

Study the effect of nickel and aluminium doped ZnO photoanode in DSSC

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ABSTRACT

Dye sensitized solar cells (DSSC) is one of the promising candidates which are efficient, low-cost, and clean hybrid molecular solar cell devices. Zinc oxide (ZnO) has been widely used as the photoanode in DSSC due to its excellent charge conduction mechanism, yet still suffers from poor cell efficiency. In this study, aluminium doped ZnO (ZnO:Al) and Ni doped ZnO (ZnO:Ni) were studied as photoanode material in DSSC using solar cell capacitance simulator (SCAPS) simulation, and the electrolyte liquid considered a single solid p-type layer as hole transporting materials. Both studied photoanodes have demonstrated better cell performance than pure ZnO photoanode due to the small amount of aluminium (Al) and nickel (Ni) impurities added have enhanced the physiochemical properties of ZnO films. A power conversion efficiency (PCE) of 3.96% was obtained at 3 mol% ZnO:Al photoanode with optimized key parameters. These simulation results proved an opportunity to improve the performance of the DSSCs via doping engineering into the ZnO photoanode.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, dye-sensitized solar cells (DSSC) have gained attention with good photovoltaic performance, specifically under low-light conditions along with flexibility in terms of color and structure. In addition, DSSC is also known for its simple fabrication procedures and low production costs. The first DSSC was reported by Regan and Grätzel in 1990s, using mesoporous titanium oxide (TiO₂) prepared from colloidal TiO₂ nanoparticles for light absorption [1]. DSSC is photo-electrochemical cell-based, in which energy generation for charge carrier transport is driven from the absorption of photon energy and produces a chemical reaction [2]. However, there are many challenges faced by DSSC to improve power conversion efficiency (PCE) without reducing the stability characteristics. Theoretically, the external circuit through the semiconductor photo anode needs to function properly so that the absorption of light by the organic dye can generate and produce a flow of current which in turn produces energy, and this is known as the electrochemical effect. The semiconductor photo-electrode layer plays an important role when current reduction occurs during the recombination of photo-generated carriers in the semiconductor which in turn reduces the efficiency of the solar cell. On the other hand, the photo-anode must be highly transparent to allow sunlight to reach the dye molecules. The concept working mechanism of DSSC was different compared to other types of the solar cell, where DSSC is a photoelectrochemical solar cell that contains a dye-sensitized

mesoporous TiO₂ work electrode (WE), a redox mediator (electrolyte) and a counter electrode (CE) [1], [3]-[5]. However, WE and CE can be (semi) transparent that allowing for illumination of the solar cell. Since the beginning of TiO₂-based DSSC research, zinc oxide (ZnO) has been the best TiO₂ alternative for DSSC. Both TiO₂ and ZnO consists same electron affinities and almost same band gap energies approximately 3.2 eV and 3.3 eV, respectively, and ZnO has much higher electron diffusivity than TiO₂ [6], [7] and higher electron mobility of 115 cm² V⁻¹ s⁻¹ -155 cm² V⁻¹ s⁻¹ [8], which is for efficient electron transport in the semiconductor and reduction of recombination rate. The electrical conductivity of ZnO can be enhanced further with a small amount of aluminium (Al) and nikel (Ni) impurities. The ion radius of Zn²⁺ (0.74 Å) are larger than Al³⁺ (0.54 Å) and Ni²⁺ (0.69 Å), therefore Zn²⁺ able to replace at the lattice site when a small quantity of Al³⁺ and Ni²⁺ enters. Subsequently, an additional dopant can be used to improve the conductivity of the ZnO photoanode while maintaining excellent transparency in the visible light region [9], [10].

In this works, the performance of DSSC with Al and Ni doped ZnO as photoanode were investigated using solar cell capacitance simulator (SCAPS) simulation software. Several key parameters including layer thickness, doping concentration, operating temperature as well as defect density were studied in order to obtain a optimum value of PCE in DSSC structure. It is observed that the electrical conductivity in ZnO photoanode is able to increase higher with dopant a small amount of material Al and Ni. The best cell performance was achieved with 3 mol% and 4 mol% Al doped ZnO photoanode, which produced PCE of 3.96%. Similarly, Ni doped ZnO photoanode of concentration 4 mol% and 6 mol% provided PCE as high as 3.9% compared to PCE without doped ZnO photoanode which is low. The PCE in DSSC is able to increase and provide best cell performance as the concentration of material increase, however at certain point, Al³⁺ and Ni²⁺ consist of a solubility limit to substitute in ZnO material and these findings were found in previous reports [9]-[12]. The obtained results can be used as a guide and direction for future device fabrication.

2. DSSC SIMULATION

SCAPS, a one-dimensional computer simulation software was used in this work where it was able to simulate the characteristics of solar cells in terms of AC and DC electricity. This simulation software is based on three coupled differential equations that is Poisson's (1) and continuity equations for holes (2) and electrons (3) where D is diffusion coefficient, ψ is electrostatic potential, q is electron charge, G is generation rate, ξ is permittivity, and n , p , n_t and p_t are free holes, electrons, trapped holes, and trapped electrons, respectively. Meanwhile, ionized acceptor-like doping concentration is denoted by N_a^- , and ionized donor-like doping concentration is denoted by N_b^- [13].

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left(-\varepsilon(x) \frac{d\psi}{dx} \right) = q [p(x) - n(x) + N_a^+(x) - N_a^-(x) + p_t(x) - n_t(x)] \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{dp_n}{dt} = G_p - \frac{p_n - p_{n0}}{\tau_p} - p_n \mu_p \frac{d\xi}{dx} - \mu_p \xi \frac{dp_n}{dx} - D_p \frac{d^2 p_n}{dx^2} \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{dn_p}{dt} = G_n - \frac{n_p - n_{p0}}{\tau_n} - n_p \mu_n \frac{d\xi}{dx} - \mu_n \xi \frac{dn_p}{dx} - D_n \frac{d^2 n_p}{dx^2} \quad (3)$$

Figure 1. The structure of DSSC with aluminium doped ZnO (ZnO:Al) or nickel doped ZnO (ZnO:Ni) photoanodes

The studied device consists of five main layers which are indium tin oxide (ITO), ZnO:Al or ZnO:Ni as photoanode, N719 dye as dye sensitizer, redox as electrolyte and platinum (Pt) as back contact as shown in Figure 1. The energy level of each layer is illustrated in Figure 2. Herein, the redox acting as an electrolyte is considered to be the solid state *p*-layer [13]. All parameters for each simulated layer are shown in Table 1. The simulation was performed under an illumination of 1000 W/m² and an air mass of 1.5 G. The main objective of this work is to investigate the effect of Al and Ni dopant on the ZnO photoanode and to optimize the key parameters of the layer, thus increase the cell efficiency value. The optimization of the main parameters of ZnO: Al and ZnO: Ni photoanodes in terms of thickness, doping concentration, operating temperature and interface defect density has been extensively studied. This work thereby provides a clear insight that with the small addition of Al and Ni dopant on the ZnO photoanode with the optimization of several important parameters has improved the efficiency of DSSC [9], [10].

Figure 2. Energy level diagram of simulated DSSC

Table 1. Parameters for DSSC layer

	ITO [14]	N719 Dye [15]	ZnO [9]	Concentration of Al (mol%) [9]				Concentration of Ni (mol%) [10]				Redox [16]
				1	2	3	4	1	2	4	6	
Thickness (nm)	60	500	220	220	220	220	220	180	180	180	180	100
E _g (eV)	3.6	2.37	3.28	3.25	3.1	3.08	3.05	3.18	3.16	3.14	3.13	1.9
X (eV)	4.1	3.9	4.4	4.4	4.4	4.4	4.4	4.4	4.4	4.4	4.4	3.79
ε/ε ₀	10	30	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	10
N _c (1/cm ³)	2.2× 10 ¹⁸	2.4× 10 ²⁰	3× 10 ¹⁸	3× 10 ¹⁸	3× 10 ¹⁸	3× 10 ¹⁸	3× 10 ¹⁸	3× 10 ¹⁸	3× 10 ¹⁸	3× 10 ¹⁸	3× 10 ¹⁸	6.0× 10 ²¹
N _v (1/cm ³)	1.8× 10 ¹⁹	2.5× 10 ²⁰	1.7× 10 ¹⁹	1.7× 10 ¹⁹	1.7× 10 ¹⁹	1.7× 10 ¹⁹	1.7× 10 ¹⁹	1.7× 10 ¹⁹	1.7× 10 ¹⁹	1.7× 10 ¹⁹	1.7× 10 ¹⁹	6.0× 10 ²¹
μ _e (cm ² /V _s)	50	5	43.00	14.03	13.84	13.35	15.02	36.73	37.01	35.49	55.39	0.1
μ _h (cm ² /V _s)	75	5	31	31	31	31	31	31	31	31	31	0.3
N _D (1/cm ³)	1× 10 ¹⁹	0	2.9× 10 ¹⁵	7.2× 10 ¹⁸	1.02× 10 ¹⁹	1.46× 10 ¹⁹	1.06× 10 ¹⁹	6.09× 10 ¹⁸	7.53× 10 ¹⁸	8.14× 10 ¹⁸	8.80× 10 ¹⁸	1× 10 ¹⁵
N _A (1/cm ³)	0	1× 10 ¹⁷	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1× 10 ¹⁵
V _e (cm/s)	1× 10 ⁷	1× 10 ⁷	1× 10 ⁷	1× 10 ⁷	1× 10 ⁷	1× 10 ⁷	1× 10 ⁷	1× 10 ⁷	1× 10 ⁷	1× 10 ⁷	1× 10 ⁷	1× 10 ⁷
V _h (cm/s)	1× 10 ⁷	1× 10 ⁷	1× 10 ⁷	1× 10 ⁷	1× 10 ⁷	1× 10 ⁷	1× 10 ⁷	1× 10 ⁷	1× 10 ⁷	1× 10 ⁷	1× 10 ⁷	1× 10 ⁷

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Effects of Al and Ni doped ZnO photoanode in thickness

In the structure of a solar cell, the thickness of the layer plays a very important role in improving cell performance. Here, the layer thicknesses for Al doped ZnO (ZnO:Al) and Ni doped ZnO (ZnO:Ni) photoanodes were varied with different dopant concentrations in the range of 5 nm to 1000 nm for SCAPS simulations. PCE for both ZnO:Al and ZnO:Ni photoanodes showed a gradual increase with layer thickness as shown in Figure 3. However, this trend was different for ZnO photoanodes with no dopant addition, where PCE had declined sharply by 20% at 100 nm thickness compared to 5 nm thickness. This trend persists with no significant change with further increase in layer thickness. It was also found that, concentrations of 3 mol% – 6 mol% Al and Ni doped ZnO photoanodes have shown higher PCE values for all layer thicknesses compared to others by achieving PCE values as high as 3.9%. The increase in cell efficiency at higher Al and Ni doped ZnO photoanode layer thicknesses can be attributed to enhanced photon absorption,

producing more electron hole pairs and thus increasing charge carrier conduction. However, the trend is the differ for pure ZnO without doping, where there is a decrease in PCE with increasing layer thickness. This is probably due to the development of surface containing valleys and peaks at higher thickness [17], [18]. In addition, the chance for recombination to occur is high which results in a decrease in PCE and this is due to the charge requiring a longer journey to conduct current and thus generate energy [19].

Figure 3. PCE for Al and Ni doped ZnO photoanodes with different dopant concentrations at different layer thicknesses

3.2. Effects in doping density (N_D)

The doping density of ZnO:Al and ZnO:Ni photoanode were varied from $1 \times 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ to $1 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. Figure 4(a) and Figure 4(b) show similar trend curve where the PCE of ZnO:Al and ZnO:Ni photoanode rises gradually as the doping density increases. The increase in photoanode doping concentration will enhance the conductivity and reduce the reverse saturation current, thus leading to PCE growth [20]. Generally, the conductivity (σ) in N-type doping is establish as:

$$\sigma = nq\mu_n \tag{4}$$

Where n is the electron concentration, μ_n is the electron mobility and q is the electric charge. The equation in low doping were obtain as:

$$\sigma \approx N_d q \mu_n \tag{5}$$

Where $n \approx N_d$ and N_d is the ionized donor concentration. The positive correlation between σ and N_d occurs since the mobility does not change substantially with N_d in case of low doping. It can also be observed that PCE grows slowly as the doping density exceeds 10^{15} cm^{-3} . The Moss-Burstein effect will create substantial doping effects if doping density continues to rise to a certain point which will limit the DSSC performance [21].

Figure 4. Effect of the doping concentrations on the PCE for (a) Al doped ZnO photoanodes DSSC and (b) Ni doped ZnO photoanode DSSC

3.3. Effects of Al doped ZnO and Ni doped ZnO at different working temperature

In thin film solar cell applications, the operating temperature has a considerable impact on device performance. The solar cell panels are expected to be functional at temperatures above 300 K. So, in this investigation, operating temperature for both Al and Ni doped ZnO are analyzed from ranged 300 K to 400 K to understand its effect on the cell performance. It can be observed that all PCE devices performance slightly decrease as the temperature rises, approximately by -0.02 ± 0.01 %/K hence proving that an increase in temperature causes an impact on all parameter as shown in Figure 5. As the temperature rises, all parameter includes the material carrier concentration, band gaps, electron and hole mobility values changed, resulting in a reduced cell efficiency [22]. In addition, the significant absorption of energy by electrons at high temperatures causes the efficiency of solar cells to decline with temperature. The electrons are stimulated to move to an unstable state and trigger recombination before entering the conduction band [19], [23].

Figure 5. Effect of increasing temperature to the ZnO, ZnO:Al and ZnO:Ni photoanodes DSSC

3.4. Effects in defect density

The parameters of the interface layer have a great influence on the performance of solar cells. The interface layer quality depends on defect density, where higher defect density generating the recombination rate, thus decreasing the quality of the interface layer. To observe the effect in interface layer of N719 Dye/ZnO:Al and N719 Dye/ZnO:Ni, defect density was varied from range $1 \times 10^{10} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ to $1 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. At lower value of defect density, ZnO photoanode without doped obtained the lowest PCE which is around 3.06% compared to photoanode with Al doped ZnO and Ni doped ZnO. Furthermore, PCE for N719 Dye/ZnO:Al and N719 Dye/ZnO:Ni interface layer began to show a downward trend at value of $1 \times 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ which can be seen in Figure 6. PCE defect density decreased due to a lower charge recombination rate and carrier recombination at the N719 Dye/ZnO interface, which was achieved by a lower concentration of surface defects in ZnO material [24]. Furthermore, if the interface layer defect density continues to increase, the DSSC performance will degrade because high defect densities in N719 Dye/ZnO:Al and N719 Dye/ZnO:Ni lead to increase the traps and form the recombination centres [25].

The optimum PCE values for each Al-doped ZnO and Ni-doped ZnO photoanode in DSSC that obtained from layer thickness, doping density, operating temperature and defect density are shown in Table 2. It is observed that 3 mol% - 6 mol% concentration of Al and Ni yield highest PCE through out the studies. This demonstrate that by adding a small amount of Al and Ni material can increase the performance of ZnO in their electrical conductivity.

Table 2. Optimum PCE for Al and Ni dopant concentration in ZnO photoanode

Photoanode	Dopant concentration (mol%)	CE (%)
ZnO	ZnO	3.7
Al doped ZnO	1	3.85
Al doped ZnO	2	3.91
Al doped ZnO	3	3.96
Al doped ZnO	4	3.96
Ni doped ZnO	1	3.86
Ni doped ZnO	2	3.89
Ni doped ZnO	4	3.9
Ni doped ZnO	6	3.9

Figure 6. Cell performance with increasing interface defect density for different dopant of Al doped ZnO, Ni doped ZnO and ZnO photoanode DSSC

4. CONCLUSION

Herein, we report the effect of Al and Ni impurities in ZnO photoanode of DSSC on cell performance using SCAPS-1D. DSSC has been successfully simulated with different doping concentrations along with optimization of several key layer parameters. Cell efficiencies as high as 3.96% and 3.9% were obtained using above 3 mol% ZnO:Al photoanode and 4 mol% ZnO:Ni photoanode, respectively. The cell performance obtained was enhanced than that found in pure ZnO photoanode DSSC, indicating that the additional dopant had improved the charge carrier conduction and thus increased the PCE. However, further increase in dopant concentration above 6 mol% will result in deterioration of cell performance due to larger particle size and Burstein-Moss effect. So, this work thereby provides a clear insight that the addition of dopants into ZnO photoanodes with optimized key parameters has successfully improved the performance of DSSC cells. The addition of Ni and Al dopants has contributed to an increase in cell efficiency and in turn further elevates PCE. This is most probably due to the radius of Al³⁺ and Ni²⁺ of 0.54 Å and 0.69 Å, respectively, are smaller than the Zn²⁺, 0.74 Å. Therefore, the Al³⁺ and Ni²⁺ ions can sneak in and replace the Zn²⁺ ions at the lattice site as well as passivate any possible defect in the ZnO photoanode. The results obtained are useful as a guide and direction in the manufacture of future devices.

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REFERENCES

- [1] B. O'Regan and M. Grätzel, "A low-cost, high-efficiency solar cell based on dye-sensitized colloidal titanium dioxide films," *Nature*, vol. 353, pp. 737–740, 1991, doi: 10.1038/353737a0.
- [2] K. Sharma, V. Sharma, and S. S. Sharma, "Dye-Sensitized Solar Cells: Fundamentals and Current Status," *Nanoscale Research Letters*, vol. 13, no. 381, 2018, doi: 10.1186/s11671-018-2760-6.
- [3] X. Chen and S. S. Mao, "Titanium dioxide nanomaterials: synthesis, properties, modifications, and applications," *Chemical reviews*, vol. 107, no. 7, pp. 2891–2959, 2007, doi: 10.1021/cr0500535.
- [4] N. S. Nooraid, *et al.*, "Current advancement of flexible dye sensitized solar cell: A review," *Optik*, vol. 254, no. 381, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.ijleo.2021.168089.
- [5] D. Bera, L. Qian, T.-K. Tseng, and P. H. Holloway, "Quantum dots and their multimodal applications: a review," *Materials*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 2260–2345, doi: 10.3390/ma3042260.
- [6] R. Vittal and K. -C. Ho, "Zinc oxide-based dye-sensitized solar cells: A review," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 70, pp. 920–935, 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2016.11.273.
- [7] N. S. Nooraid, F. Arith, A. N. Mustafa, M. A. Azam, S. H. M. Suhaimy, and O.A. Al-Ani, "Effect of Low Temperature Annealing on Anatase TiO₂ Layer as Photoanode for Dye-Sensitized Solar Cell," *Przegląd Elektrotechniczny*, vol. 97, pp. 12–16, 2021. [Online]. Available: <http://w.pe.org.pl/articles/2021/10/3.pdf>
- [8] E. M. Kaidashev *et al.*, "High electron mobility of epitaxial ZnO thin films on c-plane sapphire grown by multistep pulsed-laser deposition," *Applied Physics Letters*, vol. 82, no. 22, p. 3901, 2003, doi: 10.1063/1.1578694.
- [9] M. M. Rahman *et al.*, "Effect of Al Doping on Structural, Electrical, Optical and Photoluminescence Properties of Nano-Structural ZnO Thin Films," *Journal of Material Science Technology*, vol. 28 No. 4, pp. 329–335, 2012, doi: 10.1016/S1005-0302(12)60064-4.
- [10] M. Y. Ali, M. K. R. Khan, A. M. M. T. Karim, M. M. Rahman, and M. Kamruzzaman, "Effect of Ni doping on structure, morphology and opto-transport properties of spray pyrolysed ZnO nano-fiber," *Heliyon*, vol. 6, no. 3, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e03588.

- [11] H. Singh and V. Kumar, "Effect of Ni doping on the photovoltaic conversion efficiency of ZnO nanostructured dye sensitized solar cells," *International Journal of Scientific Research in Physics and Applied Science*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 50-54, 2018, doi: 10.26438/ijrps/v6i3.5054.
- [12] N. S. N. M. Alias, F. Arith, A. N. M. Mustafa, M. M. Ismail, S. A. M. Chachuli, and A. S. M. Shah, "Compatibility of Al-doped ZnO electron transport layer with various HTLs and absorbers in perovskite solar cells," *Applied Optics*, vol. 61, no. 15, pp. 4535-4542, 2022, doi: 10.1364/AO.455550.
- [13] M. Burgelman, J. Verschraegen, B. Minnaert, and J. Marlein, "Numerical simulation of thin film solar cells: practical exercises with SCAPS," in *Proceedings of NUMOS (Int. Workshop on Numerical Modelling of Thin Film Solar Cells, 2007)*, pp. 357-366, doi: 1854/11121.
- [14] A. Chihi, M. F. Boujamil, and B. Bessais, "Investigation on the Performance of CIGS/TiO₂ Heterojunction using SCAPS Software for Highly Efficient Solar Cells," *Journal of Electronic Materials*, vol. 46, pp. 5270-5277, 2017, doi: 10.1007/s11664-017-5547-0.
- [15] F. Jahantigh and M. J. Safikhani, "The Effect of HTM on the performance of solid-state dye-sensitized solar cells (SDSSCs): a SCAPS-1D simulation study," *Applied Physics A.*, vol. 125, no. 276, 2019, doi: 10.1007/s00339-019-2582-0.
- [16] M. Mehrabian and S. Dalir, "Numerical Simulation of Highly Efficient Dye Sensitized Solar Cell by Replacing the Liquid Electrolyte with a Semiconductor Solid Layer," *Optik*, vol. 169, pp. 214-223, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.ijleo.2018.05.059.
- [17] T. A. N. Peiris, H. Alessa, J. S. Sagu, I. A. Bhatti, P. Isherwood, and K. G. U. Wijayantha, "Effect of ZnO seed layer thickness on hierarchical ZnO nanorod growth on flexible substrates for application in dye-sensitized solar cells," *Journal of Nanoparticle Research*, vol. 15, 2013, doi: 10.1007/s11051-013-2115-2.
- [18] R. Pietruszka *et al.*, "New efficient solar cell structures based on zinc oxide nanorods," *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, vol. 143, pp. 99-104, 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.solmat.2015.06.042.
- [19] N. S. Noorasis, F. Arith, A. Y. Firhat, A. N. Mustafa, and A. S. M. Shah, "SCAPS Numerical Analysis of Solid-State Dye-Sensitized Solar Cell Utilizing Copper (I) Iodide as Hole Transport Layer," *Engineering Journal*, vol. 26, no. 2, pp. 1-10, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.engj.org/index.php/ej/article/view/4414>
- [20] L. Lin, L. Jiang, P. Li, B. Fan, and Y. Qiu, "A modeled perovskite solar cell structure with a Cu₂O hole-transporting Layer enabling over 20% efficiency by low-cost low-temperature processing," *Journal of Physics and Chemistry of Solids*, vol. 124, pp. 205-211, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.jpics.2018.09.024.
- [21] K. R. Adhikari, S. Gurung, B. K. Bhattarai, and B. M. Soucase, "Comparative study on MAPbI₃ based solar cells using different electron transporting materials," *Physica Status Solidi (c)*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 13-17, 2016 doi: 10.1002/pssc.201510078.
- [22] B. M. Soucase, I. G. Pradas, and K. R. Adhikari, "Numerical Simulations on Perovskite Photovoltaic Devices," in *Perovskite Materials: Synthesis, Characterisation, Properties, and Applications*, LDN, UK: InTechOpen, 2016, Ch. 15-16, doi: 10.5772/61751.
- [23] O. V. Aliyaselam, F. Arith, A. N. Mustafa, M. K. Nor, and O. A. Al-Ani, "Solution processed of solid state HTL of CuSCN layer at low annealing temperature for emerging solar cell," *International Journal of Renewable Energy Research*, vol. 11, no. 2, 2021. [Online]. Available: https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Faiz-Arith/publication/347877587_Investigation_of_CopperIThiocyanate_CuSCN_as_a_Hole_Transporting_Layer_for_Perovskite_Solar_Cells_Application/links/610565871e95fe241a9e4b7d/Investigation-of-CopperIThiocyanate-CuSCN-as-a-Hole-Transporting-Layer-for-Perovskite-Solar-Cells-Application.pdf
- [24] Y. -Y. Lou, S. Yuan, Y. Zhao, Z. -Y. Wang, and L. -Y. Shi, "Influence of defect density on the ZnO nanostructures of dye-sensitized solar cells," *Advances in Manufacturing*, vol. 1, pp. 340-345, 2013, doi: 10.1007/s40436-013-0046-x.
- [25] K. Tan, P. Lin, G. Wang, Y. Liu, Z. Xu, and Y. Lin, "Controllable design of solid-state perovskite solar cells by SCAPS device simulation," *Solid State Electronics*, vol. 126, pp. 75-80, 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.sse.2016.09.012.

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